

2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for the Estimation of Barium

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Barium-2,3,4-trihydroxyacetophenone system in an aqueous medium showed a broad absorption maximum at 560 nm ($\epsilon_{560} = 1.27 \times 10^3$ litres/mole-cm). It has a violet-green colour. The optimum conditions for the spectrophotometric determination are: pH range 11.8-12.4; concentration range of barium 22-75 ppm for a 10 ml of $8 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent in a total volume of 25 ml; absorbance measurements must be made within the interval of 15 to 60 minutes. Beer's law is obeyed at 560 nm for the concentration range of 45-130 ppm of barium (1-cm cell). An error of +2% at a barium concentration of 60 ppm was observed for vanadate, chromate, manganese(II) and uranyl (4 ppm) ions. The presence of calcium, strontium and iron(III) causes an appreciable error; magnesium (20 ppm) completely coprecipitates barium.

BOTH direct and indirect procedures for the photometric determination of barium have been reported. Indirect methods, with all their limitations, are common in use due to a limited report on the spectrophotometric determinations of barium. The methods involved the precipitation of barium as barium chromate¹ or barium molybdate²; these methods were further extended for the indirect determination of sulphate³. Sulphazone III⁴ and its derivatives⁵ give colour-reactions with calcium, strontium and barium. Sulphazone III forms a weak complex with barium in the pH range 1.9 to 2.8; molar absorptivity at 642 nm varies in the range 1.5×10^4 to 4.0×10^4 in this pH range; the indicator also absorbs appreciably at this wave length. 2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone was found to give stable colours with the alkaline earth cations in an alkaline medium⁶. The characteristic stable colour of calcium⁷ enabled to study its spectrophotometric determination at 540 nm in a pH range 11.2 to 12.0. The present paper reports the spectrophotometric study of barium-2,3,4-trihydroxyacetophenone system at 560 nm in a pH range 11.8 to 12.4.

Experimental

2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone (THAP) was synthesized by following the literature procedure⁸. The absorbance measurements were done on Beckman DU spectrophotometer using a matched pair of 1.002 cm corex glass cuvettes. The pH measurements were done with Radiometer pHM4a pH meter. The Radiometer G200B glass electrode (recommended for the solutions of high pH) and the Radiometer K100 calomel electrode were used.

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Stock solutions: Standard solution of barium was prepared by dissolving 4.885 g of barium chloride dihydrate (AR) in distilled water to a volume of 1 litre. The barium content was checked gravimetrically as sulphate⁹. The stock solution thus prepared was exactly $2 \times 10^{-3} M$, and the concentration of stock solution of 2,3,4-trihydroxyacetophenone (Solution S) prepared in water was exactly $8 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Order of Addition of Reagents: The colour reactions of barium-THAP system is time dependent; so, for the precise measurements the following order of addition of reagents is recommended: an appropriate volume of the THAP solution is added to the barium solution and the pH is adjusted with a rapid mixing of the final solution. The reverse addition of the reagents gives low values of the absorbance probably due to the formation of a colloidal suspension.

Absorbance spectrum: A solution of 4 ml of barium stock solution and 5 ml of THAP (Solution S) was adjusted to pH 12.0 while diluting with water to exactly 25 ml (Solution A). An appropriate blank was prepared in a similar manner except that water was added in place of barium solution. Absorbance measurements were made in the region 480-680 nm within the time interval of 20 min and 60 min after the adjustment of pH. The reagent showed an absorption below 480 nm⁶, and a broad absorbance band due to barium-THAP complex was observed at 560 nm (Fig. 1) with the molar absorptivity of 1.27×10^3 litres/mole-cm.

Rate of Reaction and Stability: Solution A showed no change in absorbance measurements at 560 to 620 nm during the time interval of 20 mins and 60 mins; within the first 15 mins, there was a rapid decrease in absorbance and after 60 mins there was a slow decrease in absorbance (Fig. II). In further experiments, the absorbance measurements were

FIG. I ABSORPTION SPECTRUM OF Ba^{2+} (4 ml OF $2 \times 10^{-3} M$)-THAP (5 ml OF $8 \times 10^{-3} M$) SYSTEM AT pH 12.0 (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

FIG. II VARIATION IN ABSORBANCE WITH TIME OF Ba^{2+} (4 ml OF $2 \times 10^{-3} M$)-THAP (5 ml OF $8 \times 10^{-3} M$) SYSTEM AT pH 12.0 (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

FIG. III VARIATION IN ABSORBANCE WITH THE VARIATIONS IN pH OF Ba^{2+} (4 ml OF $2 \times 10^{-3} M$)-THAP (5 ml OF $8 \times 10^{-3} M$) SYSTEM (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

FIG IV JOB'S METHOD OF CONTINUOUS VARIATIONS FOR Ba²⁺-THAP SYSTEM AT pH 12.0 (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

FIG V MOLE RATIO METHOD FOR Ba²⁺ (4 ml of 2 × 10⁻³ M)-THAP SYSTEM AT pH 12.0 (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

FIG VI BEER'S LAW FOR Ba²⁺-THAP (10 ml of 8 × 10⁻³ M) SYSTEM AT pH 12.0 (TOTAL VOLUME 25 ml)

made at a time interval of 30 mins after the adjustment of *pH*. The absorbance of a solution stored in a stoppered flask in the dark at 0°–5° remained constant for about 15 hr.

Effect of pH : Absorbance measurements, on a series of solutions similar to solution A, were made at 560 and 620 nm in a *pH* range 9.0 to 13.0. (Fig. III) The variation in absorbance in the *pH* range 11.8 to 12.4 was less than 0.6%.

Mole Ratio Studies : The empirical formula for the most predominant barium-THAP solution complex was assigned by using the continuous variations method¹⁰, and the mole ratio method¹¹. The results (Figs. IV and V) indicated the probable 1 : 1 :: metal : reagent mole ratio, BaR, as the composition for the most predominant complex. The shape of the curves indicate the probable presence of the 1 : 2 complex, BaR₂, in equilibrium.

The results of mole ratio method suggest that a solution containing 4 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ barium solution requires at least 3 ml of $8 \times 10^{-3}M$ THAP solution to give the constant absorbance, which remains constant upto the addition of maximum 15 ml of THAP solution.

Conformity to Beer's Law : A number of solutions containing the varying amounts of barium and 10 ml of the $8 \times 10^{-3}M$ THAP solution in a volume of 25 ml at a *pH* 12.0 ± 0.1 were prepared and tested for the confirmation of the colour system for Beer's Law (Fig. VI). It was followed at 560 nm over the concentration range 45 to 130 ppm of barium for 1.0 cm cells; the absorbance readings were low below 40 ppm of barium.

Photometric Sensitivity : The optimum precision range for the spectrophotometric measurements¹² is between 0.2 and 0.7 absorbance, which corresponds to barium concentration from 38 to 75 ppm. The absorbance measurements were reproducible within a photometric sensitivity of 0.35 ppm of barium for $A = 0.001$.

Effect of Diverse Ions : The effect of different inorganic and organic species on barium determinations was studied for solutions containing 66 ppm of barium, 15 ml of $8 \times 10^{-3}M$ THAP solution, and the varying concentrations of each ion to be tested in a total volume of 25 ml at *pH* 12.0 ± 0.1 . The absorbance measurements showed an appreciable error for the solution containing even 2 ppm of calcium, strontium and iron(III). The presence of magnesium (20 ppm) has coprecipitated barium. A +2% error was observed for the presence of 4 ppm of vanadate, chromate, manganese(II) and 25 ppm of molybdate, zirconium and thorium ions.

Discussion

There are only a few reagents reported for the direct spectrophotometric determination of barium. The new reagent, 2,3,4-trihydroxyacetophenone does not absorb significantly at the absorbance maximum (560 nm) of its barium complex. The barium-2,3,4-trihydroxyacetophenone complex has a violet-green colour. Absorbance of the barium-reagent complex is reasonably constant over a time interval of 20 to 50 mins. Readings of barium-reagent system were made after a time interval of 30 mins from the preparation of solutions. The colour reaction studied in the present work is reversible which is an essential condition for most of the photometric determinations.

Calcium and strontium interfere due to the colour formation with the reagent. Magnesium does not react with the reagent but coprecipitates barium completely; hence it is necessary to separate magnesium from barium.

The presence of alkali halides decreases the molar absorptivity; it is, therefore, necessary to establish a calibration curve of barium for solutions containing the appropriate concentration of the alkali halide.

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